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AGROVOLTAICS AS A FACTOR IN STRENGTHENING ENERGY SECURITY AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN UKRAINE

Amid a full-scale war and systematic attacks on Ukraine's energy infrastructure, the issue of energy security has become critically important. The destruction of power generation and transmission facilities, capacity shortages, and reliance on centralized energy systems significantly increase the national economy's vulnerability. The situation has a particularly significant impact on the agricultural sector, a strategic, energy-dependent industry. Under these conditions, there is a strong need to implement innovative approaches to ensuring energy supply, among which agrivoltaics plays a special role.

Agrovoltaiics is a modern technology that involves the simultaneous use of land resources for agriculture and electricity generation using solar panels. This approach not only optimizes the use of agricultural land but also creates new opportunities for integrating the agricultural and energy sectors. Scientific studies emphasize that agrivoltaiics forms a fundamentally new economic model that combines food and energy security into a single system [2].

The relevance of agrivoltaiics development in Ukraine stems from several factors. First, the country has significant solar energy potential due to its favorable climate. Second, the availability of large tracts of agricultural land creates the conditions for the large-scale implementation of agrivoltaiic systems. Third, current challenges related to the war and the need for post-war reconstruction require new approaches to economic development and ensuring its sustainability.

Recent Ukrainian studies confirm the significant potential of agrivoltaiics as a tool for sustainable development. In particular, it is noted that implementing such systems enables efficient use of land resources without reducing productivity, which is important for Ukraine's agriculture-oriented economy [4]. Furthermore, international experience shows that even partial implementation of agrivoltaiics can yield significant electricity generation, helping reduce dependence on traditional energy sources [2].

One of the main advantages of agrivoltaiics is its ability to enhance energy security. In today's environment, the decentralization of the energy sector has become a prerequisite for its effective functioning. Agrivoltaiic systems promote the development of distributed generation, helping reduce load on centralized grids and increase their resilience to external factors. Generating electricity directly at the point of consumption enables agricultural enterprises to meet their own energy needs and reduce dependence on external suppliers. This is particularly important during power outages, which can lead to significant economic losses.

Furthermore, agrivoltaics contributes to increasing the energy autonomy of rural areas. In many regions of Ukraine, rural communities suffer the most from energy supply instability. The installation of local solar power plants in conjunction with agricultural activities enables the creation of energy-independent farms, an important step toward establishing a sustainable energy system for the country as a whole. As noted in studies, the development of agrivoltaics contributes to the formation of a new energy architecture based on the principles of decentralization and flexibility [5].

Another important aspect is the interaction between agricultural production and solar energy. Unlike traditional solar power plants, agrivoltaic systems do not take land out of agricultural use. The panels are positioned to ensure sufficient light for the plants. In some cases, they even create favorable conditions for crop growth by mitigating the effects of extreme temperatures and retaining soil moisture. Research findings indicate that properly designed such systems achieve an optimal balance between crop yields and electricity generation [3].

From an economic standpoint, agrivoltaics is an effective development tool. It enables agricultural enterprises to diversify their income sources, which is particularly important amid market instability. Generating additional revenue from electricity sales or reducing energy consumption enhances the financial stability of farms. Furthermore, the development of agrivoltaics stimulates investment in renewable energy, supports job creation, and contributes to infrastructure development in rural areas. Furthermore, agrivoltaics can play a significant role in Ukraine's post-war recovery. It creates opportunities to revive economic activity in affected areas by providing both energy and the conditions for agricultural production. The development of energy-independent agricultural clusters could become a key focus in the reconstruction of regions that have suffered significant destruction. In this context, agrivoltaics is considered a key tool for ensuring sustainable development [1].

However, despite its promising prospects, the development of agrivoltaics in Ukraine is hampered by several challenges. Among the main ones is the underdeveloped regulatory framework governing the combination of agricultural activities and electricity generation. Another significant barrier is the high initial investment costs, which may be unaffordable for small and medium-sized farmers. Furthermore, insufficient awareness of agrivoltaics' benefits and opportunities limits its adoption.

Addressing these challenges requires the creation of a comprehensive government policy to promote agrivoltaics. This policy should establish advantageous conditions for investment, incorporate financial incentives, and promote the development of scientific research and educational programs. Moreover, it is essential to consider international experience and tailor it to Ukrainian circumstances. As studies note, it is precisely the combination of state support and private initiatives that can ensure the successful implementation of this technology [5].

Agrovoltaics has significant development prospects in Ukraine. Given the need to restore energy infrastructure and transition to sustainable development models, agrivoltaics could become a key driver of economic transformation. Its implementation will contribute not only to strengthening energy security but also to improving resource

efficiency, developing rural areas, and increasing the competitiveness of the agricultural sector.

Thus, agrivoltaics is a promising tool that combines the potential for energy transformation and economic development. It enables efficient use of land resources, ensures energy autonomy, and creates new economic opportunities. In today's context, agrivoltaics can become a key element of Ukraine's sustainable development strategy, ensuring its energy resilience and economic growth.

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